

Policy Brief

ABS and DSI in Marine Microbiome Research

– Implications for policy, open science and innovation

1. Executive Summary and Key Messages

Marine microbiomes – the vast communities of microorganisms in our oceans – hold immense potential for innovation in health, industry, and environmental sustainability. Harnessing this potential requires navigating international rules on Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) of genetic resources, including those derived from the application of the Nagoya Protocol, in force since 2014. Meanwhile, the rise of **Digital Sequence Information (DSI)** – genetic sequence data sourced from biodiversity – is transforming research and raising new policy challenges. This policy brief distills insights from the EU-funded **BlueTools** project’s webinar and international sources to guide EU and Member State policymakers. Key messages and recommendations include:

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- **ABS Implementation – Streamline and Support:**

- *Over a decade on, the Nagoya Protocol’s bilateral approach has raised awareness and compliance, but diverse national ABS laws and procedures have created complexity, delays, and “jurisdiction shopping” by researchers. Providing abundant and clear information to access seekers, simplifying access procedures and building capacity in provider countries are critical to make ABS work for both science and conservation.*

- **DSI and Open Science – A New Paradigm:**

- *Digital sequence information is now integral to microbiome research. International consensus is forming around a multilateral DSI benefit-sharing mechanism that preserves open access to data while ensuring fairness. The EU and its Member States should actively shape this mechanism, ensuring it doesn’t undermine the open science data ecosystems that drive innovation. European engagement in DSI policy must align conservation goals with innovation, supporting capacity building for biodiversity-rich countries, strengthening compliance support within the EU and promoting awareness among researchers and industry.*

2. ABS from the Use of Genetic Resources: Lessons from >10 Years of the Nagoya Protocol

2.1 Lessons Learned from >10 Years of implementation of the Nagoya Protocol

The **Nagoya Protocol** (2010) is a supplementary agreement under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) that provides a legal framework for **access to genetic resources and fair and equitable sharing of benefits** arising from their utilization. It entered into force on October 12, 2014 and has been ratified by 142 countries (including all EU Member States). Provider countries exercise sovereignty over genetic resources in their jurisdiction (per CBD Article 15) and may regulate access and benefit sharing conditions. User countries commit to ensure compliance by researchers and companies within their jurisdiction. The EU implemented Nagoya via Regulation 511/2014, establishing a **due diligence** obligation and checkpoints (e.g. at research funding and patent application stages) to monitor compliance. Under Nagoya, **benefits** shared can be monetary (e.g. royalties, fees) or non-monetary (e.g. joint research, training), aiming to support conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.

The following lessons can be extracted from the past 11 years of application of the Nagoya Protocol:

- **Diverse National Frameworks & Complexity:** Over the past decade, countries have implemented Nagoya with widely varying national ABS laws, definitions of genetic resources and procedures. The lack of uniformity means users must deal with multiple jurisdictions, often requiring local legal counsel to ensure compliance. This is a relevant fact for the 31% of the users who have requested access to genetic resources in other countries (according to a survey carried out by the BLUETOOLS project).
- **Administrative Burdens and Delays:** A common experience has been that securing **consent permits and terms for sampling** can be time-consuming – sometimes years – due

to administrative hurdles. Moreover, access to **microbial community samples** can magnify these difficulties, since describing the genetic resource precisely ex ante is not straightforward. Such burdens have led to “**jurisdiction shopping**”, where researchers choose to work in countries with simpler or more efficient ABS processes.

- **Limited Capacity and Awareness:** Many provider countries face **capacity constraints** in implementing ABS and user countries face low awareness in the scientific community (according to the survey carried out during a workshop on DSI organized by BLUETOOLS project, 48% of the respondents have never requested access to genetic resources). However, awareness has grown through the necessity of legal compliance for publishing or funding. For instance, Spain has seen a steady yearly rise in access requests and authorizations.
- **Positive Outcomes and Evolving Best Practices:** Despite challenges, **benefit-sharing agreements** have financed conservation trusts, research collaborations, and capacity-building in provider countries. The requirement to **reinvest benefits in biodiversity** may be built into laws, aligning ABS with conservation, as in the case of Spain. For best practices, Brazil is a notable example, with a fast online registration system and benefit-sharing obligations only at commercialization.
- **Maintaining Trust and Ethical Engagement:** Nagoya was born from developing countries’ demand for fairness in biodiversity use. Compliance with ABS is a commitment to equity and conservation. The scientific community has an obligation to “deal with the system in a reasonable way” and contribute to biodiversity conservation, and legislators have an obligation to make sure the system is workable.

2.2 Policy Recommendations for ABS for the use of genetic resources

To strengthen ABS for genetic resources, European and national policymakers should pursue actions that simplify processes, enhance capacity, and foster compliance:

1. **Streamline Access Procedures:** Simplify and harmonize ABS permit processes to reduce unnecessary burdens. This includes clearer guidance and single-window, fast, online application systems to navigate different countries' requirements, expedite processing, reduce delays, and discourage "jurisdiction shopping".
2. **Build Capacity in Provider Countries:** Increase support for **capacity-building** and legal infrastructure in biodiversity-rich countries. Through development aid, technical training, and exchange programs, the EU can help partner countries establish effective ABS frameworks (e.g. trained staff, databases of national genetic resources, clear guidelines for applicants).
3. **Promote Best Practices and Legislative Coherence:** Policymakers should study and disseminate examples like Brazil's ABS law revision, which demonstrates how easing access (while maintaining benefit obligations) can increase compliance. The EU ABS framework could incorporate flexibility for different sectors, e.g. microbial research, where samples are complex mixtures of individuals with low commercial value.
4. **Enhance ABS Compliance Support:** Within Europe, continue to strengthen compliance, with robust checkpoints (e.g. ABS compliance declarations when publishing or patenting research on genetic resources) but also providing help-desks or online resources to assist researchers in meeting their obligations. In fact, 37% of the participants in our survey who have requested access to genetic resources, did not receive any assistance, 19% have used online resources (infographics, webpages, webinars) or received assistance from colleagues. **Regular dialogues** between competent authorities, research institutions, and industry can identify pain points in compliance and update guidance accordingly.
5. **Link Benefits with Conservation and Communities:** Policymakers should reinforce the principle that benefits shared are reinvested in conservation and local communities. Embedding this principle into laws (e.g. Spain) and, promoting **non-monetary benefits** (collaborative research, technology transfer, training) can build both trust and scientific capacity in provider countries.

By implementing these recommendations, EU and Member State policymakers can help ensure that the Nagoya Protocol's second decade delivers greater **legal certainty, fairness, and scientific collaboration** – protecting biodiversity while enabling innovation.

3. Benefit Sharing from the Use of Digital Sequence Information (DSI)

3.1 What is DSI, State of the Art in Benefit sharing, Conflicts and Technical Impediments

"**Digital Sequence Information**" (DSI) generally refers to digital data derived from genetic resources – most commonly, nucleotide sequence data (DNA/RNA sequences) stored in databases, but also associated data like amino acid sequences or digital genomic descriptors. DSI has become central to microbiome research, where data is publicly shared to accelerate discovery. However, this raises a crucial question: **if researchers can use a digital sequence of a genetic resource without accessing the physical material, should benefit-sharing obligations still apply?**

Global Policy Response

The draft COP-16 decision (CBD/ COP/16/L.32/Rev.1) adopted a landmark decision to **establish a global fund – the "Cali Fund" – for fair and equitable benefit sharing from DSI**. This **multilateral mechanism** will collect contributions from users of DSI and allocate benefits broadly (e.g. to conservation projects, global capacity-building), without tracing every sequence back to its country of origin in individual negotiations. Benefit sharing includes **monetary contributions** from commercial users of DSI, based on use and ability to pay, and **non-monetary benefits** to support global capacity. According to the COP-16 draft, companies

above a certain size threshold are expected to contribute ~1% of profits or 0.1% of revenue derived from DSI-utilizing activities. These indicative rates and thresholds will be finalized at COP-17. Importantly, public research institutions, universities, and *open-access sequence databases* are **not required to pay** into the fund, acknowledging that fundamental research and data infrastructure should remain unhindered. The **Cali Fund** starts as a voluntary mechanism, but COP-16 also **"invites Parties and others to incentivize contributions"** from users in their jurisdictions, through national policies to ensure companies pay into the system.

To improve **traceability and transparency**, the decision calls on sequence database providers (like INSDC databases EMBL-EBI, GenBank, DDBJ) to request metadata on the country of origin for genetic sequences (when known) and to inform users about the requirement to share benefits if they generate monetary gains using the data. However, **open access to DSI will be maintained** – keeping the mechanism consistent with open-science principles (FAIR data, CARE principles for indigenous data, and the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science).

In parallel, other international forums are aligning. The new **UNCLOS Agreement on Marine Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ)** agreed in 2023 includes provisions for benefit sharing from marine genetic resources (including DSI from areas beyond national waters). This synergy ensures that DSI will have a **coherent global benefit-sharing approach**.

Conflict with Open Science and Researchers' needs

Open access to genetic data is a cornerstone of modern biology: researchers publish sequence data in public repositories (like GenBank, EMBL-EBI's ENA, DDBJ) as a condition of journal publication. In the survey conducted by the BLUETOOLS project, 36% of the professionals consider that DSI is crucial for their work and 21,5% use it occasionally. Open Science accelerates discovery, but if new ABS rules were to impose restrictions on this data (e.g. paywalls, requirement to obtain consent before data use), it would **undermine decades of progress** in making scientific data a global public good. For this reason, *data which has been already published must remain freely accessible* for science to advance. Moreover, *public databases should remain open*, while playing a pivotal role in **signposting**, e.g. by reminding users that "if datasets are for commercial purposes, benefit-sharing is required under CBD". Moreover, new metadata requirements must not compromise the efficiency and openness of data submission and access.

The emerging multilateral approach decouples *data access from benefit obligations*. Open science is preserved (no conditional access to data), and benefit-sharing is handled through downstream contributions. However, ensuring users actually comply with expected contributions is not straightforward, which is why COP-16

invites **national measures to incentivize compliance**. Policymakers will need to translate this into action (potentially through domestic legislation or tax incentives).

Technical Impediments

Unlike physical samples, digital data can be copied endlessly and flows globally. **Tracking the origin of every sequence in a researcher's analysis is technically very difficult** – the origin of sequences is not always annotated in databases. Moreover, a single research project might analyse millions of sequences from hundreds of organisms: linking each to a benefit-sharing obligation would be unfeasible. Nevertheless, databases will ask data submitters to include country of origin information **where available**, to provide transparency on sample origin. However, there are tens of millions of legacy sequences already in databases that will never have reliable origin metadata. Those sequences are considered *part of the public domain* and available for use without new conditions.

Another concern is **enforcement and monitoring**. How do we know when a company has used DSI and made a product or profit from it? Patent offices could be one checkpoint, similarly to the current disclosure of Nagoya compliance. Companies in sectors like pharma or biotech typically know if they utilized genetic sequences in developing a product. The COP-16 draft suggests certification of compliance upon contribution to the Cali fund, to enhance reputation or for legal assurance when marketing products globally.

Aspect	Physical genetic resources	Digital sequence information
Legal Approach	Each use of a genetic resource requires negotiation of PIC & MAT with the provider country. User country laws enforce compliance	Users globally contribute to a collective fund for benefit sharing. No direct negotiation with individual countries for each data use
Coverage	Material samples of genetic resources within national jurisdiction acquired after Nagoya's entry into force. Traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources is also covered.	Digital data derived from genetic resources. <i>Publicly available DSI</i> that is not covered by other ABS agreements falls under the mechanism.
Access to Resources	Access to biological material requires prior consent from provider country and mutually agreed terms	<i>No prior consent</i> needed for DSI access. Users are informed of benefit sharing obligations if DSI used for profit
Benefit Sharing	Benefits (monetary or non-monetary) are negotiated in MAT and often realized only if a product/material is commercialized. Enforcement relies on compliance checks	Monetary benefits are collected as a percentage of revenue/profit from DSI utilization. All Parties will collectively decide use of funds. Non-monetary benefits are channeled through global platforms. Certificates may be issued to contributors to show compliance
Challenges	Varied national laws and administrative hurdles; difficulties in monitoring compliance. Few cases lead to significant monetary benefits.	Varied national laws and administrative hurdles; difficulties in monitoring compliance. Few cases lead to significant monetary benefits.

3.2 Policy Recommendations for DSI Benefit-Sharing

To achieve a fair DSI benefit-sharing system without hindering science, EU and Member State policymakers should:

- **Incentivize Industry Contributions:** Develop **domestic policies or legislation** that incentivize companies profiting from DSI to share benefits. This could include reporting requirements for large life-science companies on their DSI use, tax breaks or certificates of compliance for those who contribute.
- **Ensure legal certainty and a clear license-to-operate** to ensure future investments in research and innovation projects by industry. Companies need assurance that contributions to, e.g., the Cali Fund fully satisfy their benefit-sharing obligations, without risk of overlapping national requirements or retroactive claims. The mechanism must be simple, predictable, and proportionate – avoiding complex tracking of DSI use or ambiguous definitions of “direct” and “indirect” benefit. Contribution rates must be meaningful and fair; applying them to a company’s total revenue – particularly for diversified enterprises not primarily focused on biotechnology – risks imposing costs that are not economically viable and will hinder innovation.
- **Protect Open Access Data:** Enshrine in policy that **open access to scientific data is to be maintained**. The EU’s open science policies (such as Horizon Europe’s open data requirements) should explicitly integrate with ABS/DSI rules: researchers should not be asked to restrict data sharing. Support European and international data repositories in implementing the COP-16 measures, like capturing metadata and displaying user notices, in a way consistent with the FAIR principles.
- **Invest in Global Capacity and Technology Transfer:** Direct a significant portion of benefit sharing (both monetary and non-monetary) to **capacity-building in developing countries**, e.g. fund training programs, bioinformatics infrastructure, and research collaborations in countries that provide genetic resources to also become users of DSI for their own development.
- **Engage Stakeholders in Policy Design:** Continue the dialogue with scientists, database curators, industry, and indigenous/local community representatives as DSI policies are implemented. The BlueTools/BlueRemediomics webinar itself is a model for such multistakeholder engagement.
- **Harmonize with Other Regimes:** Ensure that EU and national policies on DSI benefit-sharing are coherent with other international regimes, such as the BBNJ agreement for high seas genetic resources. A cohesive approach prevents loopholes and reduces confusion.
- **Aspects related to facilitation exploitation:** The recommendations for DSI highlight legal clarity, industry engagement and open science principles. This can be translated into regulatory instruments and create incentives. It offers a first step to the creation of a roadmap, in order to encourage investment in capacity building and research partnerships.

By taking these steps, European policymakers will help establish a **solid benefit sharing system for the genomics era** – one that continues to fuel open science while ensuring that benefits from utilizing the “digital genetic heritage” of our planet are shared fairly, supporting global biodiversity goals.

4. About the authors

BlueTools is an EU-funded Horizon Europe project (2022–2026) dedicated to unlocking the potential of marine microbiomes for a sustainable blue bioeconomy. BlueTools brings together 14 partners (eight academic teams and five industry partners across Europe, plus a training organization) to develop faster and more efficient ways to **sample and culture marine microorganisms**, advance bioinformatic pipelines to mine genomic sequences for valuable functions, and demonstration of new microbiome-based products in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, agriculture, and environmental remediation. With these technologies, BlueTools is committed to ensuring that this exploration of marine genetic resources is done **safely, sustainably, and equitably**. BlueTools works closely with its sister project **BlueRemediomics** and engages with policy and stakeholder initiatives – such as the ABS/DSI webinar that informed this brief – to contribute to responsible research and innovation. By doing so, BlueTools not only seeks scientific breakthroughs but also aims to guide policy and best practices so that marine biodiversity can be utilized for societal benefit while **preserving ocean health and ensuring fairness** to biodiversity-rich regions of the world.

Sources: This policy brief draws on discussions and insights from the *BlueTools–BlueRemediomics ABS/DSI webinar (May 2025)*, the text of the **CBD COP-16 Draft Decision on DSI**, the **German Research Foundation (DFG) statement on DSI**, and other relevant international documents and national case studies, as mentioned throughout. It is intended to inform European and national policymakers and stakeholders in navigating the complex but crucial interface of biodiversity policy, innovation and open science.

